

Study on Emotional Changes by Visual Movements and Sounds in the Virtual Space

-Focused on Cases of Producing Digital Wind-bell Applications-

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Abstract: Humans feel various emotions by and react to visual vibration of objects or auditory sense or tactile impressions. For example, people forget a hot weather by using a breeze blowing in mountains or fields or by using a fan, or feel refreshed or relaxed mentally by using various sounds caused by a wind. Effects of a wind bell lie in the ‘Refreshment’ caused by a wind and the perception of a wind through the movements of an object. In other words, it can be defined that an auditory element and visual element are perceived at the same time, doubling the coolness. Through digital contents using such a natural movement and sound, it seems possible to make Korean culture internationalized, further conducting profound researches on the delivery of emotional elements humans feel, empathy and afterimages. Therefore, this study aims to investigate how emotional feelings people have in the analog space are applied to the digital space and what effects they have on people’s sensibilities through the production of wind bells in the virtual space. It also aims to verify the emotional stability of digital wind bells and even to examine a possibility as applications.

Key words: *Windbell, Culture Interaction, Mobile Device, Emotion, Digital Contents*

1. Introduction

Humans feel various emotions by and react to visual vibration of objects or auditory sense or tactile impressions. For example, people forget a hot weather by using a breeze blowing in mountains or fields or by using a fan, or feel refreshed or relaxed mentally by using various sounds caused by a wind. Effects of a wind bell lie in the ‘Refreshment’ caused by a wind and the perception of a wind through the movements of an object. [1]In other words, it can be defined that an auditory element and visual element are perceived at the same time, doubling the coolness. Wind bells are different in material, form and size in each country, but they are all moved by winds, and the principle of making sounds with the movement is similar to one another. Especially, Korea, Japan and

China out of all the countries in Asia have different forms of bell sounds and origins of wind bells in each country. Yamashita states in his study on ‘Japanese Sense of Pitch’ that the movement and irregularity of sounds play a role in converting or calming down emotional feelings. [2] He also insists that there are always movements in all the things existing in the natural world without a halt, and there are necessarily irregular changes included in the movement. Movements necessarily include irregular changes. For instance, a wind may stop out of sudden while blowing. Likewise, there always exists vibration in the natural world, which is designated as Fractal Theory. The theory was a term created by a French mathematician called Mandelbrot in 1975, meaning general terms such as figures or phenomena not having distinctive lengths. For example, artificial structures such as automobiles, desks and buildings have a distinctive length, but things created by the natural power, such as mountains, clouds, seashores and plants don’t have a distinctive length. If we can recreate such natural movements or sounds into contents, I think it is possible to feel the comfortableness and tranquility which are felt by people through natural things via digital media. Furthermore, I think in-depth theoretical researches should be conducted on how elements of natural elements are delivered or transferred to moods of human beings. [3]

As for specific methods, the forms and kinds of traditional wind bells were investigated while digitalized wind bells in the form of portable device application were produced. This research is to investigate how the moods felt in analog through movements of wind-bells in a space or sounds in an imaginary space are applied in digital spaces and what impacts they play on the moods of human beings. By this, I also tried to confirm the verification on emotional tranquility and possibility of developing into contents at the time of having access to a digital wind-bell. I measured changes in mood states of the users for the effects of emotional transition obtained by the users through the scenes by using the manufactured wind-bell, and discovered which of the moods provided by a digital wind-bell played more importantly. [4]

With the results from the investigation, the study also aims to discuss the effects of digital wind bells as a digital therapy able to help modern people’s life as well as verify the contents of digital wind-bells.

Figure.1 Type of Wind-Bells in Asia

2. Research Experiment

2.1 Research Aim

As a basic research for production of digital sceneries, I hereby try to analyze the emotional changes and images of the respondents by a visual image of wind-bells by experiments and ascertain the effects thereof. I intend to survey the general knowledge of the respondents for wind-bells, find about emotions on a wind-bell stored in the memories of the respondents, and investigate the differences from the moods felt when it is digitally produced. For methods to measure these moods, various methods such as measurement of changes of palpitations or measurement of brain waves, etc. may be used.

In this research, a method of measuring emotions using questionnaire for POMS was used; for it is possible to emotionally quantify the changes after measuring the moods before and after the stimulus if the questionnaire for POMS is used. [5] I intend to specifically clarify the factors which impacted the changes of moods by surveying the changes of moods through the questionnaire of POMS and examine any possibility of the contents after having 20 respondents hear the sample sounds of the wind-bell. I also intend to investigate any possibility that digital wind-bell using movements or sounds provided by wind-bells can perform any therapeutic functions.

2.2 Change of Mood due to Sounds

Human beings sense sounds when their ears recognize changes of pressure transferred through the air. The functions of ears of a human being are basically grown up six months after his/her birth, and some infants can recognize sounds even when they are in the wombs of their mothers. Thus, the functions of hearing start at a very period compared to sight, sense of smell, sense of taste or tactual sense. [6] In such functional respects, it's one of the reasons that there are so many toys which generate sounds which stimulate senses of hearing among the toys for children. The ordinary functions produced by sounds such as music, conversations, alarms, etc. are quite extensive. The images or evaluation of products are sometimes changed by the sound of opening or closing of ball-point pens or fountain pens. While this sound plays a role for recognition of complete closing of a cap, such a sound sometimes affects the utility of a product. A sound is a physically stimulating factor which can be accepted by ears. But, it is not visually seen and disappears within a short period of time. [7] Even though many contents which utilize sounds are being produced, most of them are dependent on natural sounds, etc. and there are not enough in-depth researches on which of the factors of sounds emotionally affect human beings.

In this research, I intend to deeply deal with the effects on emotions of human beings provided by the visual and audial characters of wind-bells, which is a analog thing, when they are digitalized.

Figure .2 Samples of digital contents utilizing natural sounds[8]

2.3 Research Methods

Three major kinds of experiments were conducted in their contents, and the first experiment was conducting a survey of questionnaire to figure out the basic information and experiences of the respondents for wind-bells. Secondary, changes of moods before and after watching a digital wind-bell were measured by using a questionnaire of POMS.[9] Thirdly, an SD measurement method was conducted to measure the images of the suggested digital wind-bell. For the scales of adjectives used in the experiments, the scales of 16 adjectives having corresponding relations to each other which were used in 'Report on Scientific Survey of Minds Required by Societies' by Niikura were used. [10]

Table 1. Contents of Experiments

Questionnaire	Change of Mood before and after Stimulus(POMS)	Evaluation on Impression of Stimulus	Visual Images of Wind-bell Used in Experiments
Survey on degree of experiences of wind-bells	Measurement of differences of changes of moods before and after impression of visual images of a digital wind-bell through POMS	Evaluation on impression of recognition obtained after experiencing a digital wind-bell (SD method)	

1) Research Process

The process of experiments is as follows:

- ① The basic knowledge and whether or not having experience are specifically surveyed using a questionnaire.
- ② The moods of respondents are measured before watching a digital wind-bell using a questionnaire of POMS.
- ③ A visual image of iPod touch digital wind-bell is activated and the respondents watch it for two minutes with earphones in their years.
- ④ The moods of the respondents are measured again after completion of watching the visual image by using the questionnaire of POMS.
- ⑤ The moods of the respondents are surveyed after the experiments by POMS.
- ⑥ The impressions of the experienced digital wind-bell after watching the visual image are surveyed by using the SD yardstick.

2) Basic Survey on Experience of Sceneries

The respondents are composed of 20 persons, of which 8 persons are male and 12 persons are female, who are in their 20's and 30's who are supposedly using digital equipment frequently. For question on whether or not using digital equipment, 15 persons, which is more than 70 percent of the respondents, answered with using at least 5~6 hours a day, and 50 percent of the respondents answered with 'a lot' for question on the level of stress of duties. All the respondents have experience for wind-bells, and temples are the most frequent place for the experience, for which the most frequently experienced material is a material made of metal. This is maybe due to the cultural characteristics of Korea, differently from materials such as wood, glass, porcelain, etc. in China or Japan. For the question on impression when experiencing wind-bells, the majority of respondents answered with impressions of nature and peace such as 'calm, sleepy, clean, being purified' etc. due to the factors mixed with the places in which they experienced the wind-bells. It was shown that the respondents in their 20's and 30's in occupation groups using digital equipment a lot have lots of stresses generated from their duties, and the images on the wind-bells they experienced in the past have the role of making their minds peaceful.

3. Analysis and Result

3.1. POMS(Profile of Mood States)

POMS is a method of a self-evaluation type questionnaire evaluating emotional states majorly used in the area of psychiatry or neuropsychology after being reported in 1971. While 65 items showing moods or emotions were

suggested in the questionnaire of POMS, I conducted the measurement of experiments with 30 items based on the abridged version thereof for this research. A respondent himself/herself can mark the scores by assigning from 0 point if there was no mood or emotion falling under an item to 4 points if there were lots of such moods or emotions for the item. According to McNair, when asking to a subject, “past one week” is long enough to express typical and continual life style of the subject, and is short enough to reflect short-term treatment. Moreover, comparing to other tests with uncertain points of answers, “states” can be distinguished from “tendency” by limiting the period. Moreover, short-term expression like “present”, “today”, “past three minutes” can be evaluated by query. Grading system is same as 65 question version. The inspector should check that all questions are marked clearly, and then calculate total ratings of each category by 5 questions. Comparing to 65 question version, this test had very short test time and small burden on the subject, which makes it useful to inspect tendency of change by certain period. Moreover, grading time is also short and the inspector can present the result of the test right after the test. [11,12,13]

Classification of scoring results into 6 yardsticks of moods:

◇T-A: (Tension-Anxiety) 「Spirit is tense」 「Anxious」 : If this score is high, it represents that the respondent is more tense.

◇D:(Depression-Dejection) 「Depressed」 : If this score is high, it represents that the respondent has lost his/her self-confidence more than usual.

◇A-H:(Anger-Hostility) 「Get angry」 「Get hostile」 If this score is high, it represents that the respondent is angry.

◇V: (Vigor) 「Vigorous」 : As this item is a positive item, different from other five yardsticks, if this score is low, it represents that the respondent gets less vigorous.

◇F: (Fatigue) 「Fatigued」 : If this score is high, it represents that the respondent is very tired.

◇C: (Confusion) 「Confused」 : If this score is high, it represents that the respondent is confused and his/her mind is not organized.

I have analyzed the differences of the moods before and after the experiments based on the results after conducting surveys using 30 items of the abridged version of POMS to the 20 respondents.

1) Measurement before Watching Wind-Bells

Table 2. Result of Survey of POMS before Experiments

Respondent	Sex	Age	T-A	D	A-H	V	F	C	TOTAL
1	Female	26	12	15	18	4	15	6	58
2	Female	24	15	20	19	12	10	11	65
3	Female	25	17	19	20	12	13	16	65
4	Female	29	13	17	19	10	12	14	57
5	Female	26	12	11	17	13	9	9	53
6	Female	31	20	20	20	11	19	17	73
7	Male	25	18	20	19	15	12	18	68
8	Female	25	17	20	20	13	18	19	69
9	Male	32	17	19	19	8	12	18	57
10	Female	28	18	19	19	19	17	17	75
11	Female	25	18	17	19	14	13	12	69
12	Female	33	10	20	18	13	19	13	67
13	Female	24	13	11	10	12	12	11	47
14	Male	29	14	17	17	5	13	9	57
15	Male	29	14	11	11	11	10	9	48
16	Male	30	14	16	16	7	14	15	52
17	Male	29	16	20	19	12	19	16	70
18	Male	27	14	11	17	16	5	10	53
19	Female	28	15	20	19	12	10	6	65
20	Male	27	14	11	11	11	10	9	57
AVERAGE		27.6	15.05	16.7	17.35	11.5	13.1	12.75	61.25

2) Measurement after Watching Wind-Bells

Table 3. Result of Survey of POMS after Experiments

Respondent	Gender	Age	T-A	D	A-H	V	F	C	TOTAL
1	Female	26	13	14	20	9	13	12	57
2	Female	24	20	20	20	14	12	18	68
3	Female	25	18	18	20	13	18	15	72
4	Female	29	18	16	20	12	15	17	64
5	Female	26	19	19	20	20	16	13	81
6	Female	31	10	13	19	20	19	19	62
7	Male	25	18	20	19	18	15	18	72
8	Female	25	18	20	20	14	17	19	70
9	Male	32	19	14	18	5	11	14	53
10	Female	28	19	19	20	20	16	17	77
11	Female	25	17	14	19	17	11	11	67
12	Female	33	12	20	18	16	19	16	69
13	Female	24	11	11	10	11	11	7	47
14	Male	29	13	14	20	9	13	12	57
15	Male	29	20	18	19	15	15	18	69
16	Male	30	12	12	12	11	11	12	46
17	Male	29	17	20	19	14	19	17	72
18	Male	27	15	15	20	19	9	14	64
19	Female	28	20	20	20	14	12	18	68
20	Male	27	20	18	19	15	15	18	69
		27.6	16.45	16.75	18.6	14.3	14.35	15.25	65.2

3) Comparison between Measurements before and after Experiments

I examined on the significance of the differences due to being prior to and after the experiments and differences in sex through variance analysis of the scores obtained from the surveys of POMS before and after the experiments.

Table 4. Comparison of Measurements before and after the Experiments

	Measurements before the Experiments	Measurements after the Experiments	Comparison of Measurements before and after the Experiments (P<0.05)
T-A	15.05	16.45	0.2091
D	16.7	16.75	0.9887
A-H	17.35	18.6	0.1996
V	11.5	14.3	0.0318
F	13.1	14.35	0.2856
C	12.75	15.25	0.0560
TOTAL	61.25	65.2	0.1959

As a result thereof, it was found that the higher scores for 'V'(Vigor) which represents vigor or activity after the experiments was significant, and the tendency of higher scores of 'C'(Confusion) which means confusion after the experiments. However, generally speaking, the significant difference for other categories other than the 'V' category was not verified due to individual differences, even though it was shown that the evaluation scores of surveys of POMS got higher after the experiments.

3.2 Evaluation on Impression of Visual Image of Wind-Bell

Evaluations on impressions were conducted to the respondents by using the SD method for the impressions after watching the visual image of wind-bells with 16 items. Evaluations were obtained by using 5 yardsticks of [significantly it is, it is, neither side, it is, significantly it is], and the evaluations of the respondents were shown as the following Table 5. Based on the data thereof, analysis of main components was conducted to find the general meaning of the impressions of the respondents after watching wind-bells and to compare the characteristics of the impressions.

Table 5. Data from Evaluations of Impressions of Total Respondents

Respondent	bright	deep	complete	wide	trustworthy	rational	colorful	fun	complicated	full	clear	new	Warm	open	attractive	pleasant
1	1	1	2	2	2	-1	0	0	1	0	-1	-2	2	2	1	1
2	0	0	-1	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	1	1	-1	0	2	2
3	-1	-1	0	0	-1	0	2	0	1	1	0	1	-1	0	0	-1
4	-1	1	-1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	-1	-1	-1
5	1	-2	0	0	1	2	1	0	2	2	-1	1	1	1	0	0
6	1	1	1	1	1	-2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	1	0	1	-1	-1	0	0	1	1	1	-1	1	0	0	0	0
8	-2	-2	-1	-2	0	-1	1	0	-2	0	1	1	-2	-2	-2	-2
9	-2	2	2	1	-1	2	2	-1	2	2	0	2	-1	-1	-2	-2
10	-2	0	1	1	0	0	2	0	2	0	-1	0	-1	0	-1	-1
11	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
12	-2	1	0	1	0	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	0	0	-1	-2
13	1	-1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	-1
14	-1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	-2	0	0	0
15	-1	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	2	1	1	0	-1	0	-2	-2
16	-2	1	0	-2	1	1	1	-2	1	1	-2	1	-2	-2	-2	-2
17	-1	-1	0	-1	0	2	0	0	2	2	-1	0	-1	0	0	-2
18	-1	1	0	0	-1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1
19	-2	-2	0	-1	0	2	2	0	2	1	-1	1	-1	0	-1	-2
20	0	-1	-1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	-1	-1

Figure.3 Average of Evaluations of Impressions of Respondents

Table 6. Data for Main Components of Evaluations of Impressions

Number	1	2	3	4	5
Eigen value	5.197	2.805	2.256	1.453	1.009
Percent	32.480	17.531	14.102	9.082	6.303
Cum Percent	32.480	50.011	64.113	73.195	79.499

Number	1	2	3	4	5
bright	0.350	-0.169	-0.045	0.257	-0.113
deep	0.091	0.233	0.227	-0.457	-0.466
complete	0.165	0.123	0.422	-0.284	0.157
wide	0.289	0.196	0.265	-0.273	-0.079
trustworthy	0.200	-0.144	0.169	0.015	0.326
rational	-0.197	0.285	0.238	0.448	-0.117
colorful	-0.017	0.375	-0.144	-0.239	0.583
fun	0.290	0.115	-0.357	0.015	-0.080
complicated	0.111	0.334	0.414	0.257	0.066
full	0.092	0.443	-0.077	0.373	-0.121
clear	0.127	0.271	-0.343	-0.190	-0.316
new	-0.038	0.447	-0.254	0.0592	0.083
warm	0.329	-0.156	0.130	0.169	-0.278
open	0.386	-0.007	0.146	0.148	0.219
attractive	0.385	-0.018	-0.176	0.095	0.120
pleasant	0.388	-0.041	-0.188	-0.081	0.081

From the above results, five components with high explanatory powers for which the inherent value thereof exceeds.

Each main component could be classified as below:

- 1st main component: bright, wide, warm, open, attractive, good
- 2nd main component: faithful, new
- 3rd main component: complete, uninteresting, complicated, dull
- 4th main component: rational
- 5th main component: shallow, trustworthy, colorful

As a result, the 1st main component evaluated the comfortable and satisfactory mood, and the 2nd main component meant the evaluation giving high priority of conversion of moods, while the 3rd main component represented the evaluation of being uninteresting. The 4th main component had impressions of being rational, and the 5th main component represented impressions of something not serious and colorful, which is considered to be affected by outward impressions.

4. Conclusions

I believe that a sense of sound must be a sensitive and meticulous component of senses in emotions of human beings. It was found through this research that wind-bells have considerable influence on changing emotions or moods of people by what was produced by the shapes or movements thereof, not to mention the effects on people with sounds thereof.

This research is a basic research to assist the production of contents in the future by using wind-bells, as analog emotions were also felt by digital media. Changes of emotions by visual images of wind-bells were investigated through experiments, and it was found, as a result of measurements of the moods of the respondents by using the questionnaire of POMS before and after showing the visual images of wind-bells, that there was a significant difference for higher scores for 'V'(Vigor) which represents vigor or activity after the experiments and a tendency of getting higher scores for 'C'(Confusion) which represents confusion after the experiments. Generally, it was found that the evaluation scores for surveys of POMS got higher after the experiments, the significant difference for the categories except for the category 'V' was not verified due to individual differences. I think the moods of the whole respondents got more vigorous and comfortable after experiencing the wind-bells than before experiencing thereof. In another words, I believe that there were evaluations of fresh and vigorous thanks to the visual tranquility and audial freshness of wind-bells, and, on the contrary, a tendency of increase of confusion was also shown. I believe this was because the shifts of moods were not completely put in order as the evaluations were conducted within a short period of time. [14]

The 1st major component evaluated the comfortable and satisfactory mood, and the 2nd main component meant the evaluation giving high priority of conversion of moods. But the 3rd main component represented the evaluation of being uninteresting. I could verify that vividness was generated in the shifts of moods due to audio-visual stimulus of the digital wind-bells, and people got more comfortable and satisfied thereby. Also, even though there were shifts of moods such as confusion similar to getting excited, it was found that, in overall, people felt tranquil and comfortable by the digital wind-bells. I think the users will fully experience the analog emotions of wind-bells in the digital environment if this research is more developed and the contents are produced. I think it was meaningful to specifically verify on what emotions an audio-visual stimulus have impacts, and it is necessary to manufacture the suggested wind-bells by providing various logical standards for more diverse verifications, and more meticulous verifications including differences of moods according to the length of experiment time are needed in the future.

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